

TREATMENT OF HELICOBACTER PYLORI THROUGH THE MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) is a pathogenic bacterium commonly found in humans and widely distributed among the global population. It induces a chronic inflammatory process in the gastric mucosa resulting in symptoms such as burning sensation, dyspepsia, and epigastric pain. Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) is a diagnostic and therapeutic system developed by Isaac Goiz Durán (1941-2021) which targets the root cause of diseases and restores the body's metabolic balance. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) in treating *H. pylori* through a real case study involving descriptive and interpretative analysis of MB screenings, questionnaire interpretation, and conclusions. The results demonstrated that MB effectively combated *H. pylori* infection and improved the patient's symptoms. These findings suggest that MB may be a viable therapeutic technique when

combined with integrative medicine, offering a non-invasive, natural, and cost-effective approach to *H. pylori* treatment.

Keywords: Biomagnetic Pair; *Helicobacter pylori*; Gastritis; Ulcer; Diagnosis; Complementary therapy; Medicinal Biomagnetism.

1. INTRODUCTION

Helicobacter pylori (*H. pylori*) is a bacterium that colonizes the stomach, primarily found in the gastric fundus, body, and antrum. It establishes contact with the luminal membrane of epithelial cells in the gastric mucosal lining, which provides an ideal environment for its adaptation due to the neutral composition of gastric mucus (BLASER; BERG, 2001; LADEIRA et al., 2003; ATHERTON, 1997).

H. pylori infection is one of the most common bacterial infections worldwide affecting approximately half of the global population. Its prevalence varies with age, socioeconomic status, and ethnicity. The main routes of transmission are oral-oral and fecal-oral (POSSE et al., 2006).

The pathophysiological process involves continuous inflammation of the gastric mucosa resulting in symptoms such as burning sensation, dyspepsia, and epigastric pain. If untreated, the persistent inflammatory condition may lead to complications such as chronic gastritis, duodenal and gastric ulcers, upper gastrointestinal bleeding, and gastric cancer. Diagnosis typically involves clinical tests such as serology, endoscopy, and biopsy. Conventional medical treatment often involves medications such as antibiotics and stomach acid secretion inhibitors to promote ulcer healing and symptom improvement (SUERBAUM; MICHETTI, 2002). However, these treatments can cause adverse side effects and may be financially inaccessible to many individuals. Therefore, Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) emerges as an alternative, non-invasive, and more affordable approach to *H. pylori* infection treatment.

MB is a diagnostic and therapeutic system developed by Isaac Goiz Durán (1941-2021), a physician and physiotherapist who graduated from the Autonomous University of Puebla (1988). Durán studied various aspects of alternative

medicine, including the Energy Therapy course taught by Richard Broeringmeyer, the medical director of NASA (Kentucky, USA) and author of the book “Principles of Magnetic Therapy” (1988). These studies demonstrated the use of monopolar magnetic fields combined with kinesiology to assess the human body as an electromagnet. Based on these concepts and knowledge of physics, Goiz developed the Medicinal Biomagnetism technique, discovering the first Biomagnetic Pair (BMP) (Thymus – Rectum) while treating an HIV patient (DURÁN, 2017; BROERINGMEYER, 1991).

MB treatment involves the application of BMP where the biomagnetic charges of specific organ systems exhibit vibrational and energetic resonance. The magnets have opposite polarities: negative pole (North) and positive pole (South). Both poles resonate with each other, utilizing the geographic convention of the planet (Figure 1). The technique employs magnets with intensities ranging from 1,000 to 7,500 Gauss at specific anatomical points, aiming to rebalance the body’s metabolism (DURAN, 2017).

Figure 1. South and North poles according to their geographic correspondence on Earth.

Source: Bossa (2021).

The fundamentals of this technique establish that disease occurs due to an imbalance in the body represented by the Neutral Energy Level (pH 7.0 \pm 0.3 – NEL) which generates a Biomagnetic Pair (BMP). In this situation, each point of acidity is correlated with an alkaline zone, known as the biomagnetic resonance phenomenon. For example, in the case of the *H. pylori*, there is a resonance in the

BMP of the esophageal hiatus/testicle or vagina (alkaline and acidic zones, respectively). Based on these discoveries, Biomagnetism allows for intervention in the etiology of diseases addressing organic and glandular dysfunctions, and establishing metabolic balance by correcting pH and organism homeostasis (DURÁN, 2017).

Therefore, the objective of this study is to gather information regarding the application of Biomagnetism in the treatment of a patient diagnosed with *H. pylori* and gastric disorders.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was based on a qualitative descriptive case study. The research involved the interpretation and analysis of the medical records of a patient diagnosed with *H. pylori* and gastric disorders.

The patient voluntarily participated in this study and had a medical diagnosis of mild distal erosive esophagitis and enanthematous gastritis of the antrum with confirmed *H. pylori* presence, as determined by clinical examinations, including digestive endoscopy and biopsy conducted in June 2020, prior to MB treatment. Follow-up examinations were conducted in October 2021. The patient was a 49-year-old female who did not take any medications and resided in Taubaté, Brazil, where in-person consultations were conducted between July and October 2020.

Three consultations were conducted following the scanning protocol of MB by Bossa (2021a), and the consultation guidelines provided by Cazella et al. (2023) and Santos et al. (2023).

The methodology involved a complete scanning along with the application of predetermined protocols: basic protocol, 3D1 protocol, and gastritis symptom protocol proposed by Bossa (2021). During the scanning process, a comprehensive scan of the patient's body from head to toe was performed to identify organs or tissues that deviated from their normal polarity (pH 7.0 \pm 0.3 – NEL).

In this study, scanning was conducted using a muscle kinesiological test, a common practice among naturopaths, chiropractors, acupuncturists, and integrative medical professionals. The test involved detecting the shortening of the right hemibody, where a difference of a few centimeters could be observed in the patient's feet (Figure 2), allowing for the identification of BMP in resonance. Subsequently, magnets were applied in pairs to specific anatomical points identified during the scanning process (BRYAN, 2017; DURÁN, 2008; DURÁN, 2017; FRANK, 2017; CAZELLA et al., 2023; SANTOS et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Demonstration of the kinesiological test. A: Shortening of the right hemibody; B: Alignment of both hemibodies.

Source: BOSSA (2021).

All BMP used in the scannings were tabulated for better understanding and are presented in Tables 2 to 6. Additionally, a qualitative questionnaire consisting of seven questions regarding the patient's symptoms was conducted to analyze her perception and progress after MB treatment (Table 1). All questions were administered through an online form (Google Forms).

Table 1 – Qualitative questionnaire on patient's symptoms

Questionnaire
What were your main complaints before MB treatment?
How long had you been experiencing these complaints?
Did you undergo any treatment for these complaints prior to MB?

Did you notice improvement during MB treatment?
How do you currently feel regarding these complaints after completing the treatment?
What is your opinion of the MB treatment? (The patient was asked to rate it on a scale from 0 to 10, with 0 being the lowest score and 10 being the highest score).
Would you recommend BM to others?

Source: the authors (2021).

3. RESULTS

Three consultations were conducted with the participant, using a complete scanning, from July to October 2020. The respective scanings and their corresponding BMP were identified and impacted through the kinesiological test, as shown in Tables 2 to 7. The questionnaire and its responses are presented in Table 8, and the results of the confirmatory tests are presented in Table 9.

3.1 Scanning 1

The first consultation took place on July 6, 2020, in-person, in the city of Taubaté, Brazil. Initially, the BMP from the Basic Protocol were applied (Table 2) and remained in place for 30 minutes. Throughout this time, the complete scanning was conducted, identifying and impacting the BMP found (Table 3). After the complete scanning, all applied magnets were removed, with individual checking of each one. Next, the BMP from the symptom scanning for gastritis (Table 2) were applied for 15 minutes, followed by the BMP from the 3D1 Protocol (Table 1) also for 15 minutes.

The Basic Protocol and 3D1 Protocol aim to reduce inflammation, detoxify, and reduce abdominal swelling, while the symptom scanning target the impact of specific BMP previously described for the treatment of gastric symptoms (BOSSA, 2021b).

Table 2 – BMP of the Basic Protocol

Biomagnetic Pair	North (-) Impact Point	South (+) Impact Point
BMP 1	Liver	Liver
BMP 2	Liver	Right Kidney
BMP 3	Right Kidney/Left Kidney	Right Kidney/Left Kidney
BMP 4	Rachidian Bulb	Lumbar ³ / ₄
BMP 5	Supraspinatus (Right/Left)	Supraspinatus (Right/Left)
BMP 6	Thymus	Rectum
BMP 7	Hip (Right)	Hip (Left)
BMP 8	Cardia	Appendix
BMP 9	Transverse Colon	Liver
BMP 10	Thyroid (Right/Left)	Thyroid (Contralateral)
BMP 11	Testicle (Right/Left)	Testicle (Contralateral)
BMP 12	Lumbar	Kidney (Right/Left)

Source: BOSSA (2021b).

Table 3 – BMP of the 3DI Protocol

Biomagnetic Pair	North (-) Impact Point	South (+) Impact Point
BMP 1	Liver	Liver
BMP 2	Liver	Right Kidney
BMP 3	Right Kidney/Left Kidney	Right Kidney/Left Kidney

BMP 4	Rachidian Bulb	Lumbar ³ / ₄
BMP 5	Supraspinatus (Right)	Supraspinatus (Left)
BMP 6	Thymus	Rectum
BMP 7	Hip (Right)	Hip (Left)
BMP 8	Cardia	Appendix
BMP 9	Transverse Colon	Liver
BMP 10	Thyroid (Right)	Thyroid (Left)
BMP 11	Testicle (Right)	Testicle (Left)
BMP 12	Lumbar	Kidney (Right/Left)
BMP 13	Eye (Right)	Eye (Left)
BMP 14	Patella (Right)	Patella (Left)

Source: BOSSA (2021b).

Table 4 – BMP of the Gastritis Symptom Scanning

Biomagnetic Pair	North (-) Impact Point	South (+) Impact Point
BMP 1	Stomach	Thymus
BMP 2	Cardia	Appendix
BMP 3	Pancreatic Head	Pylorus
BMP 4	Cervical	Sacrum
BMP 5	Rachidian Bulb	Lumbar ³ / ₄
BMP 6	Cardia	Pylorus
BMP 7	Stomach	Pylorus

BMP 8	Pylorus	Pylorus
BMP 9	Stomach	Suprarenal (Contralateral)
BMP 10	Cardia	Suprarenal (Contralateral)
BMP 11	Hiatal Esophagus	Vagina (Right/Left) (Testicles)
BMP 12	Pancreatic Head	Suprarenal

Source: BOSSA (2020).

Table 5 – BMP of the Complete Scanning

Biomagnetic Pair	North (-) Impact Point	South (+) Impact Point
BMP 1	Subdiaphragm (Right)	Subdiaphragm (Left)
BMP 2	Scar	Kidney (Right)
BMP 3	Stomach	Duodenum
BMP 4	Pancreatic Body	Pancreatic Body
BMP 5	Pancreatic Body	Stomach
BMP 6	Spleen	Liver
BMP 7	Spleen	Lung (Right)
BMP 8	Spleen	Duodenum
BMP 9	Liver	Kidney (Left)
BMP 10	Pylorus	Kidney (Left)
BMP 11	Pancreatic Body	Pancreas
BMP 12	* Larynx	Parietal (Right)
BMP 13	* Esophagus	Antecuernum (Right)

BMP 14	* Trachea	Esophagus
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Source: the authors (2021). *BMP found in a focus scanning.

3.2 Scanning 2

The second session took place on July 20, 2020, in person, in Taubaté/SP. Initially, the BMP of the Basic Protocol (Table 2) were applied for 30 minutes, and during this time, the complete scanning was conducted with identification and impactation of the BMP (Table 6). After completing the scanning, all the applied magnets were removed after individual verification. Next, the Biomagnetic Pairs of the 3D1 Protocol (Table 3) were impacted for 15 minutes.

Table 6 – BMP of Scanning 2

Biomagnetic Pair	North (-) Impact Point	South (+) Impact Point
BMP 1	Gallbladder	Gallbladder
BMP 2	Inter Iliac	Sacrum
BMP 3	Zygomatic (Right)	Kidney (Left)
BMP 4	Parietal (Right)	Parietal (Left)
BMP 5	Parathyroid (Right)	Parathyroid (Left)
BMP 6	Eyebrow (Right)	Eyebrow (Left)
BMP 7	3rd Dorsal	7th Dorsal
BMP 8	Carina	Carina
BMP 9	**Post-Pineal	Amygdala
BMP 10	**Thymus	Hypophysis
BMP 11	***Thyroid (Right)	Thyroid (Left)

BMP 12	Pancreatic Head	Liver
BMP 13	Pancreatic Head	Pancreatic Head
BMP 14	Hepatic Ligament	Kidney (Right)
BMP 15	Cardia	Appendix
BMP 16	Stomach	Thymus
BMP 17	Iliac (Left)	Iliac (Right)
BMP 18	*Pineal	Pineal
BMP 19	* Pre-Pineal	Parietal (Right)

Source: the authors (2021). *BMP found in focus screening; **Psychosomatic BMP (Annex A); ***Hormonal BMP (Annex B).

3.3 Scanning 3

The third session took place on August 24, 2020, in person, in Taubaté/SP. Initially, the BMP of the Basic Protocol (Table 2) were applied for 30 minutes, while conducting the complete scanning with identification and impactation of the BMP (Table 7). After completing the scanning, all the applied magnets were removed after individual verification. The session concluded with the application of the BMP of the 3D1 Protocol (Table 3) for 15 minutes.

Table 7 – BMP of Screening 3

Biomagnetic Pair	North (-) Impact Point	South (+) Impact Point
BMP 1	Urethra (Superior)	Urethra (Inferior)
BMP 2	Inter Iliac	Sacrum
BMP 3	Middle Deltoid (Right)	Middle Deltoid (Left)

BMP 4	Iliac Crest (Right)	Iliac Crest (Left)
BMP 5	Ulna (Right)	Ulna (Left)
BMP 6	Pubis	Hiatal Esophagus
BMP 7	Appendix	Thymus
BMP 8	Appendix	Bladder
BMP 9	Retro Tensor Fasciae Latae (Left)	Retro Tensor Fasciae Latae (Left)
BMP 10	Urethral Sphincter	Urethral Sphincter
BMP 11	Armpit (Left)	Armpit (Right)

Source: the authors (2021).

3.4 Questionnaire

This questionnaire was designed to evaluate the qualitative response of the patient's body to the MB treatment and to assess the improvement, according to the patient's own perception of their symptoms. Six descriptive questions with short answers were formulated and answered through the Google Forms platform (Table 8).

Table 8 – Qualitative Questionnaire.

QUESTION	ANSWER
What were your main complaints before the Medicinal Biomagnetism treatment? Please mention and describe if possible.	Severe stomach pain, pain in the esophagus, abdominal pain, and intense heartburn.
How long did you suffer from these complaints?	7 years

Did you undergo any treatment for these complaints before the Medicinal Biomagnetism treatment?	Yes, I tried many antibiotics, but none provided relief or a solution.
Did you observe improvement during the Medicinal Biomagnetism treatment?	Yes, initially my stomach hurt a lot, but as the treatment progressed, I experienced incredible improvement until the symptoms completely disappeared.
What did you think of the Medicinal Biomagnetism treatment? Please rate it on a scale of 0 to 10, with 0 being the lowest and 10 being the highest.	At first, I was a bit apprehensive and skeptical, but as I started seeing results, it became an amazing and new experience for me. I would rate it 10.
Would you recommend Medicinal Biomagnetism to others?	Yes.

Source: the authors (2021).

After the completion of the three sessions, the patient was advised to repeat the endoscopy with biopsy. The initial examinations were conducted on June 15, 2020, and the follow-up examinations on October 7, 2021. The delay in the post-treatment examination was due to the waiting time within the city's public healthcare system (SUS – Sistema Único de Saúde). The diagnostic results from the endoscopy and pathological analysis are described in Table 9.

Table 9 – Diagnostic conclusion of the gastric endoscopy and pathological analysis of the patient before and after the MB treatment.

PRE-TREATMENT ENDOSCOPY	POST-TREATMENT ENDOSCOPY
Mild distal erosive esophagitis	No findings

Mild enanthematous gastritis of the antrum	Mild enanthematous gastritis of the antrum
PRE-TREATMENT PATHOLOGICAL	POST-TREATMENT PATHOLOGICAL
Moderate chronic gastritis	Gastric mucosa with chorion ectasia
Positive <i>H. pylori</i> test result	Negative <i>H. pylori</i> test result

Source: the authors (2021).

4. DISCUSSION

The *Helicobacter pylori* is known for its association with gastroduodenal diseases, intestinal inflammation, gastroesophageal reflux, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, hepatocellular carcinoma, cholelithiasis, and cholecystitis. However, some studies suggest that it may also influence the development and severity of other extragastric diseases, such as anemia due to decreased levels of iron and vitamin B12; neurological disorders like multiple sclerosis, Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Guillain-Barré syndrome, cardiovascular disorders, and dysregulation of insulin levels, which may increase the risk of diabetes (SANTOS et al., 2020).

All these symptoms occur due to its ability to penetrate the gastric mucosal layer, as it synthesizes lipases and proteases that degrade the mucous layer, facilitating its entry and development in the stomach. It also produces other enzymes such as superoxide dismutase, catalase, and arginase, which provide protection against the immune system's activities, preventing an effective immune response against this pathogen (LADEIRA et al., 2003; KODAIRA et al., 2002).

Thus, this bacterium induces an inflammatory response in the gastric mucosa becoming one of the main causes of chronic gastritis. In children, it causes recurrent abdominal pain, chronic diarrhea, and even stunted growth. Therefore, it is believed that *H. pylori* infection is acquired in childhood and remains latent for decades or even a lifetime (KODAIRA et al., 2002; LADEIRA et al., 2003).

Despite being a well-known infection, there is still no natural and effective treatment for combating *H. pylori* without the use of medication.

Therefore, with the progressive increase in *H. pylori* resistance and the emergence of new strains resistant to antibiotics, there is a growing demand for combined use of different types of antibiotics, often requiring prolonged treatment for approximately 14 days. This type of treatment has shown positive results, but there is always a need for new studies to explore the use of new medications due to bacterial resistance (O'Connor et al., 2010; Infante-Molina et al., 2017).

Thus, Medicinal Biomagnetism emerges as a cost-effective, non-invasive, and potentially effective alternative, as demonstrated in this case study where the patient not only experienced symptom improvement early in the treatment but also obtained positive results in her follow-up examinations.

The technique of BMP was developed 33 years ago and has since proven to be effective in the treatment of a variety of clinical conditions, including infectious diseases such as *H. pylori* (BRYAN, 2017). In this study, satisfactory results were observed in the evaluated patient, as the infection by the bacterium was contained after undergoing MB treatment. Her improvement was also noticeable to herself, as reported in the questionnaire (Table 8) conducted after the treatment. Even before completing her treatment, the patient reported an improvement in discomfort and symptoms of stomach pain, esophageal pain, heartburn, and abdominal pain.

Isaac Goiz Durán dedicated his life to the study of BMP, but little has been done to scientifically validate his work. Therefore, this study becomes of great importance and contribution to MB. His theory states that when the BMP are active and the magnets are properly positioned, remaining under the patient's body for a sufficient period of time tend to treat the damaged tissues, and as a result, microorganisms no longer thrive or reproduce. Thus, these invading organisms are eliminated within a matter of days (BRYAN, 2017; DURÁN, 2017; 2008).

The correlation between Isaac Goiz Durán's theory and this present study leads us to consider that it culminated in the elimination of the *H. pylori*. In the first session, the BMP Hiatal Esophagus/Vagina (Table 4), which is the specific point for impacting the bacterium, appeared to be worked on, corroborating this relationship. However, another BMP referred to as an irregular pair that it was not present in the scanning protocol referred to as a "focus pair," emerged for impacting *H. pylori*, such as the BMP larynx/parietal D (Table 5), suggesting that the bacterium had more than one point of biomagnetic resonance in this patient.

We can also suggest that the other BMP worked on during the complemented scanning and even benefited the patient's treatment, such as the BMP spleen/liver, which impacts *Brucella abortus* and is associated with symptoms of gastritis and discomfort; the BMP pancreas body/pancreas body, which addresses digestive disorders; the BMP zygomatic (Right)/kidney (Left), which impacts *Plasmodium vivax* and sustains symptoms of discomfort, stomach acidity, and abdominal pain; the BMP pancreas head/liver, which impacts *Clostridium botulinum* and symptoms of gas, colic, stomach pain, and intestinal problems; and the BMP liver/kidney (Left) and pylorus/kidney (Left), which impacted *amoeba* and worked on symptoms of intestinal disorders and gas (Table 5).

Similar results, which support those of this study, were demonstrated by Cazella et al. (2023) in their case study on urinary tract infections caused by the bacterium *Escherichia coli*. The BMP used to aid in the elimination of the bacteria and reduce the symptoms of infection yielded satisfactory results after treatment with MB, as was also observed in the present study.

Further evidence of the benefits of MB treatment may also be seen in the study by Martinii et al. (2023). After three MB sessions, the decrease in PSA levels and the regression of prostate adenocarcinoma to a milder chronic inflammation suggested that MB was a favorable factor in achieving these positive results.

Therefore, we suggest that MB may be recommended as an accessible, efficient, and less invasive alternative treatment for *H. pylori* infection and gastric disorders.

5. CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that Biomagnetic Pair Therapy (BMP) may be an effective, beneficial, cost-effective, and low-risk alternative without adverse effects for the treatment of *H. pylori* infection and associated digestive disorders. The efficacy of MB was confirmed through post-treatment clinical examinations, despite the delay in conducting these examinations. These results showed successful eradication of the bacterial infection and improvement in patient symptoms, as reported by the patient herself in the questionnaire. Although the final examination results still indicated the presence of moderate gastritis, the patient no longer experienced gastric pain and discomfort. The observed improvements likely initiated shortly after the application of the BMP during the first session, as the body initiated its natural process of recovery and homeostasis. This study represents a pioneering effort in the field of MB treatment. Therefore, we recommend further large-scale studies to provide additional scientific evidence that supports the integration of MB as a complementary approach to conventional treatment methods for *H. pylori*.

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